

Perception of Pregnant Women Regarding Neonatal Jaundice

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ABSTRACT

Background: Jaundice is a clinical condition in the newborn that requires medical attention and most common cause of admission in the 1st week of life in neonatal intensive care unit.

Objective: This study aimed to assess the perception of pregnant women by their knowledge and attitude regarding neonatal jaundice.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted from 1st January 2021 to 31st December 2021 on 270 pregnant women, who were selected by purposive sampling from Pirganj upazilla Health complex and selected community clinics at Thakurgaon district of Bangladesh. Data were collected by face-to-face interviews through a pretested, semi-structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed by SPSS.

Results: The findings of the study indicate that the mean age of the participants were 24.71(±3.6) years. Among the participants 69.6% (188) of pregnant women had moderate knowledge, 24.4% (66) had good knowledge and 5.9% (16) had poor knowledge. 48.5% (131) of pregnant women had moderate attitude, 47% (127) good attitude and 4.4% (12) had poor attitude regarding neonatal jaundice. Most of the pregnant women had lack of knowledge about treatments and preventive measures of neonatal jaundice.

Conclusion: The findings of the present study showed that there was a need for increasing the awareness of mothers on all aspects of neonatal jaundice such as causes, side effects, prevention and emergency referral to doctors to prevent irreversible complications.

KEYWORDS: Neonatal jaundice, Perception, Knowledge, Attitude, pregnant women.

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INTRODUCTION

Neonatal jaundice (NNJ) is a common clinical condition in newborns, characterized by yellowish discoloration of the skin and sclera due to elevated serum bilirubin levels. While most cases are physiological and self-limiting, untreated severe hyperbilirubinemia can result in kernicterus, cerebral palsy, developmental delay, and even neonatal death (Bhutani et al., 2016). Globally, NNJ affects more than half of newborns within the first week of life, and it remains a leading cause of preventable neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (Olusanya et al., 2015).

Pregnant women's perception and knowledge of NNJ are vital because they are usually the primary caregivers in the neonatal period. Early recognition of symptoms and prompt health-seeking behavior depend on maternal awareness and understanding. However, studies from different regions have shown gaps in awareness and misconceptions. For instance, in Nigeria, although 77% of expectant mothers had heard of NNJ, the majority demonstrated poor knowledge regarding its causes (69.5%) and appropriate treatment (72.1%) (Egube et al., 2021). Similar findings were reported in Ghana, where most mothers had heard of NNJ but only 7.4% could identify correct causes (Amegan-Aho et al., 2019).

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In Nepal, nearly half (49.9%) of mothers had poor knowledge about NNJ, with only a very small proportion (2%) aware of phototherapy as a treatment (Shrestha et al., 2019). Likewise, in Ethiopia, only 39.2% of mothers demonstrated adequate knowledge, with maternal education, urban residence, and antenatal care significantly associated with awareness levels (Tiruye et al., 2021). In Saudi Arabia, more than 60% of mothers showed poor knowledge, influenced by age, education, parity, and previous experience with NNJ (Al-Ali et al., 2019). A study in Egypt also highlighted that cultural beliefs and reliance on traditional remedies continued to delay timely care (El-Farrash et al., 2016).

Encouragingly, interventions such as structured antenatal health education have been shown to significantly improve knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding NNJ. A controlled trial demonstrated that prenatal training enhanced recognition of symptoms, understanding of risk factors, and awareness of effective treatments such as phototherapy (Zhu et al., 2015).

Assessing pregnant women's perception of NNJ is therefore essential for designing targeted health education strategies. Strengthening maternal awareness has the potential to reduce preventable complications and improve neonatal survival.

This study aims to assess the perceptions (knowledge and attitudes) of pregnant women regarding neonatal jaundice, identify socio-demographic and obstetric factors associated with their understanding, and explore common misconceptions influencing their health-seeking behaviors.

Materials and Methods

Study design: This study was a descriptive type of Cross Sectional Study.

Study place: a. Upazila Health Complex at Pirganj Thana, Thakurgaon district.

b. Keutgaon community clinic of Pirganj Thana, Thakurgaon district.

c. Mallikpur community clinic of Pirganj Thana, Thakurgaon district.

Study population: Pregnant women attending Upazila Health Complex and selected community clinics at Pirganj thana of Thakurgaon District.

Study period: The study was conducted during a period of one year from 1st January to 31st December, 2021.

Sampling technique and sample size: Calculated sample was 344 by using convenience sampling technique. However, due to time constraints and participant availability during the study period, data were successfully collected from 270 respondents.

Data collection instruments: A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data.

Data collection procedure: At first, purpose of the study was informed to the respondents. A complete assurance was given that all information would be kept confidential. Informed consent was obtained from respondents. Data was collected by face to face interview. Each respondent was interviewed separately and confidentiality was maintained strictly.

Data analysis: The data collected from the respondents were analyzed. After completion of data collection, the data were checked and edited manually and verified before tabulation. Data were coded, entered and analyzed in a computer. The statistical analysis was using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics was used for all variables; values were expressed as frequencies and percentage.

Ethical considerations: Ethical clearance of the study was taken from the International Review Board (IRB) and written informed consent was taken from the respondents. Privacy and confidentiality was maintained strictly.

RESULTS

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents (n=270)

Age of the respondents (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
19 - 24	126	46.6
25 -29	100	37.0
30-34	43	16.0
≥35	1	0.4
Mean ± SD	24.71± 3.60	
Educational qualification of the respondents		
Illiterate	67	24.8
S.S.C	97	35.9
H.S.C	71	26.3
Graduate	32	11.9
Post-graduate	3	1.1
Occupation of the respondents		
Home maker	201	74.4
Business	4	1.5
Farmer	1	.4

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Laborer	15	5.6
Service holder	42	15.6
Student	7	2.6
Total	270	100

Table 1 showed out of 270 respondents 46.6% (126) were in between 19-24 years and 37% (143) of the respondents age were between 25-29 years ,only 0.4%(1) of the respondent age were on ≥ 35 years. Mean age of the respondents were

24.71 \pm 3.60 (SD). From the total respondents, 24.8% (67) were illiterate, majority 35.9 % (97) were completed S.S.C and only 1.1% (3) were post-graduate and from them, 74.4% (201) were home maker, and only 0.4 % (1) was farmer.

Table 2: Knowledge of respondents regarding Neonatal Jaundice (n=270)

Knowledge of the respondents regarding skin color of neonate during neonatal jaundice	Frequency	Percentage (%)
No	17	6.3
Yes	253	93.7
Knowledge of the respondents regarding appearing jaundice during the first 36 hours is normal		
No	162	60
Yes	108	40
Knowledge of the respondents regarding breast feeding prevents jaundice in their infants.		
No	105	38.9
Yes	165	61.1
Knowledge of the respondents regarding prematurity is a risk factor for neonatal jaundice		
No	71	26.3
Yes	199	73.7
Knowledge of the respondents regarding phototherapy is a treatment of neonatal jaundice		
No	155	57.4
Yes	115	42.6
Knowledge of the respondents regarding Severe jaundice may cause death in neonates.		
No	55	20.4
Yes	215	79.6
Knowledge of the respondents regarding exposure of a jaundiced infant to the sun will increase the risk of dehydration.		
No	91	33.7
Yes	179	66.3
Total	270	100

Table 2 reveal that 93.7% of respondents recognized skin color changes as a sign of neonatal jaundice, while 40% incorrectly believed that its appearance within the first 36 hours is normal. About 61.1% were aware that breastfeeding helps prevent jaundice, and 73.7% knew prematurity is a risk

factor and only 42.6% identifying phototherapy as effective. Most respondents (79.6%) understood that severe jaundice can cause death, and 66.3% recognized that exposing a jaundiced infant to the sun increases the risk of dehydration.

Table 3: Respondents level of knowledge on neonatal jaundice (n=270)

Level of knowledge on neonatal jaundice	Frequency	Percentage
Poor knowledge	16	5.9
Average knowledge	188	69.6
Good Knowledge	66	24.4

Table 3 shows that out of 270 respondents 66 (24.4%) had good knowledge on neonatal jaundice, 188 (69.6%) had average knowledge on neonatal jaundice and 16(5.9%) had poor knowledge on neonatal jaundice.

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Table 4: Attitude of respondents regarding neonatal jaundice (n=270)

Attitude of the respondents regarding If jaundice increased, can give oral herbs.	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly disagree	5	1.9
Disagree	49	18.1
Don't know	72	26.7
Agree	129	47.8
Strongly agree	15	5.6
Attitude of the respondents regarding if jaundice increased have to consult a physician.		
Strongly disagree	14	5.2
Disagree	50	18.5
Don't know	10	3.7
Agree	155	57.4
Strongly agree	41	15.2
Attitude of the respondents regarding would consult as it is a serious condition.		
Strongly disagree	24	8.9
Disagree	117	43.3
Don't know	39	14.4
Agree	81	30.0
Strongly agree	9	3.3
Attitude of the respondents regarding afraid of hospitalization.		
Strongly disagree	28	10.4
Disagree	36	13.3
Don't know	7	2.6
Agree	166	61.5
Strongly agree	33	12.2
Total	270	100

Table 4 illustrates the attitudes of 270 respondents regarding neonatal jaundice. About half of the respondents (47.8%) agreed that if jaundice increases, oral herbs can be given, while 26.7% were uncertain and 20% disagreed or strongly disagreed. In contrast, the majority (57.4% agree, 15.2% strongly agree) believed that a physician should be consulted if jaundice worsens, although 23.7% disagreed or strongly

disagreed. Regarding whether they would consult as it is a serious condition, only 33.3% agreed/strongly agreed, while a larger proportion (52.2%) disagreed or strongly disagreed, and 14.4% were unsure. Fear of hospitalization was evident among respondents, as 61.5% agreed and 12.2% strongly agreed, whereas 23.7% either disagreed or strongly disagreed, and 2.6% were uncertain.

Table 5: Respondent's level of attitude on neonatal jaundice (n=270)

Level of attitude on neonatal jaundice	Frequency	Percentage
Poor attitude	12	4.4
Average attitude	131	48.5
Good attitude	127	47.0

Table 5 shows that out of 270 respondents 127 (47.0%) had good attitude on neonatal jaundice, 131 (48.5%) had average

attitude on neonatal jaundice and 12(4.4%) had poor attitude on neonatal jaundice.

Table 6: Believes of respondents regarding neonatal jaundice (n=270)

Opinion regarding causes of NNJ.	Responses (yes)	
	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Lack of exposure to sunlight	173	64.1%
Yellow color food ingestion	115	42.6%
Change in weather	142	52.6%
Certain medicine ingestion	57	21.1%
Opinion regarding complications of NNJ.		

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Neonatal death	180	66.7%
Brain injury	125	46.3%
Seizure	118	43.7%
Liver weakness	67	24.8%
Opinion regarding treatment of NNJ		
Exposure of sunlight	171	63.3%
Medicine and herbs	192	71.1%
Avoidance of certain food	76	28.1%
Opinion regarding prevention of NNJ.		
Exposure to sunlight	165	61.1%
Blood group test	149	55.2%
Frequent breast feeding and hygiene maintain	121	44.8%

Table 6 shows among 270 respondents, common beliefs about the causes of neonatal jaundice included lack of sunlight exposure (64.1%), change in weather (52.6%), and yellow food ingestion (42.6%). Reported complications were neonatal death (66.7%), brain injury (46.3%), and seizures (43.7%). For treatment, most suggested medicine/herbs (71.1%) and sunlight exposure (63.3%). Preventive beliefs included sunlight exposure (61.1%), blood group testing (55.2%), and breastfeeding with hygiene (44.8%).

DISCUSSION

This study explored the socio-demographic profile, knowledge, attitudes, and beliefs regarding neonatal jaundice (NNJ) among 270 respondents.

Knowledge regarding NNJ

The study revealed that most respondents recognized yellow discoloration of the skin as a sign of jaundice (93.7%), consistent with other studies in Bangladesh where mothers could identify visible symptoms but lacked understanding of underlying risk factors and management (Huq et al., 2017). However, 40% incorrectly believed that jaundice within the first 36 hours is normal, and less than half (42.6%) were aware of phototherapy as treatment. These gaps reflect patterns observed in other Bangladeshi studies, where only 30–40% of mothers had adequate knowledge of NNJ treatment options (Abdullah et al., 2021).

Internationally, similar knowledge deficits have been reported. In Nigeria, less than 50% of mothers knew that NNJ can cause death or brain injury (Ogunfowora and Daniels, 2006). In Saudi Arabia, only 28% of mothers were aware of phototherapy (Alfouwais et al., 2018), while in Ghana, misconceptions such as attributing NNJ to weather or diet were also common (Amoakoh et al., 2025). By contrast, studies in developed countries such as the UK and USA report higher maternal awareness, largely due to structured antenatal education and universal newborn screening programs (Maisels, 2015). This comparison highlights the educational gap between Bangladesh and high-income countries.

Attitudes toward NNJ

Attitudes among respondents were mixed. While 72.6% agreed that a physician should be consulted if jaundice worsens, nearly half (47.8%) also believed that oral herbs could be used, and 73.7% expressed fear of hospitalization. This reflects a dual reliance on traditional remedies and formal health services, a trend reported in several national studies (Rahman et al., 2023). Similar findings have been documented in other LMICs. In Ethiopia, for instance, herbal treatment and sunlight exposure were commonly preferred before seeking medical care (Tilahun et al., 2018). Conversely, in high-income countries, reliance on traditional remedies is rare, and early healthcare-seeking behaviors are the norm due to better access and trust in healthcare systems (Bhutani et al., 2013).

Beliefs regarding NNJ

Respondents' beliefs demonstrated the influence of cultural perceptions. More than half cited lack of sunlight (64.1%), change in weather (52.6%), and yellow food ingestion (42.6%) as causes of NNJ. Similar cultural explanations are widespread in South Asian communities, where dietary and environmental factors are often linked to neonatal illness (Abdullah et al., 2021). Internationally, beliefs vary: African studies report spiritual causes and witchcraft as perceived reasons for NNJ (Ogunfowora and Daniels, 2006), while in the Middle East, certain foods and maternal practices are commonly blamed (Alfouwais et al., 2018). These findings suggest that cultural context strongly shapes explanatory models of NNJ across countries.

National and global implications

Nationally, the findings underscore the need for improved maternal and community education in Bangladesh, particularly focusing on correcting misconceptions about causes and treatments. While awareness of severity (79.6% linking NNJ to neonatal death) was encouraging, fear of hospitalization and preference for traditional remedies may delay treatment and worsen outcomes. This reflects broader health system challenges in Bangladesh, including mistrust of hospitals, financial barriers, and limited availability of phototherapy at rural levels (Abdullah et al., 2021).

Globally, NNJ remains a leading cause of preventable neonatal morbidity and mortality, particularly in LMICs

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where health literacy is low and access to care is limited (Olusanya et al., 2018). The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes early recognition and timely treatment with phototherapy or exchange transfusion as key interventions, yet cultural practices and poor awareness often delay such care (WHO, 2019). Comparative data from high-income countries show that structured education, screening programs, and universal postnatal follow-up have significantly reduced severe NNJ and kernicterus (Bhutani et al., 2013; Maisels, 2015).

CONCLUSION

This study highlights that while most respondents could recognize the signs of neonatal jaundice, significant misconceptions remain regarding its causes, complications, and treatment. Many still relied on traditional remedies and expressed fear of hospitalization, which may delay appropriate care. These findings are consistent with other studies in Bangladesh and internationally, especially in low- and middle-income countries, where cultural beliefs strongly influence health-seeking behaviors. Strengthening community-based education, improving maternal awareness, and ensuring access to effective treatments such as phototherapy are essential to reduce the preventable burden of neonatal jaundice and align neonatal outcomes with global health standards.

RECOMMENDATION

As per the findings of the study, following recommendations are suggested:

- To improve the level of awareness and change existing attitude, educational programs must be conducted at government level.
- Female OPD, EPI centers gynecological inpatient and out-patient department may be targeted for addressing awareness program for pregnant women.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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